

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART III. N¹-AND
N⁴-SUBSTITUTED SULPHANILAMIDES, SCHIFF'S
BASES OF SULPHAPYRIDINE AND
SULPHATHIAZOLE*

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Eighteen Schiff's bases of sulphapyridine and sulphathiazole have been prepared.

In the course of the development of the chemotherapy of sulphanilamide and its derivatives, Schiff's bases have not received much attention from investigators, even though Goissedet, Despois, Galliot and Mayer (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1936, 121, 1082) announced as early as 1936, that the Schiff's bases of sulphanilamide derived from benzaldehyde and some substituted benzaldehydes were active. This result was confirmed by Buttle, Gray, and Stephenson (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 724) who prepared and tested the anils of sulphanilamide derived from *m*-nitro-, 6-nitro-, 3-hydroxy- and *p*-methoxy-benzaldehydes, cinnamic aldehyde, veratraldehyde, 3 : 4-diethoxybenzaldehyde and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde ; and in addition they reported that they were much less toxic. The next set of workers, Kolloff and Hunter (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 158) extended this field to N¹-substituted sulphanilamides, and prepared and tested a few anils of sulphapyridine also. All these workers found that the introduction of any arylidine group into the N⁴-nitrogen did not very much alter the bactericidal property, but the toxicity was considerably diminished. However, the anils derived from *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (*Chem. Rev.*, 1940, 27, 85) have been reported to be more active than the free amino compounds. The few anils of sulphapyridine that have been made so far by Kolloff and Hunter, viz. those of benzaldehyde, cinnamaldehyde, 2-nitro-, 4-nitro-, 3-hydroxy-, *p*-methoxy- and *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehydes have all been found to possess good therapeutic properties and low toxicity. Apart from these few anils of sulphapyridine, no systematic investigation seems to have been undertaken on the study of the Schiff's bases of the two well reputed drugs, viz., sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine. It therefore seemed of interest to synthesise a series of Schiff's bases of a sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine using particularly those aldehydes which have proved effective in the case of similar compounds derived from sulphanilamide itself.

The usual method of preparation of the Schiff's bases is by reacting molecular proportion of the aldehyde and the sulphanilamide compound in boiling alcoholic solution as indicated by Buttle, Gray and Stephenson (*loc. cit.*). But after many trials the best method has been found to be the direct fusion of the appropriate aldehyde with the sulphanilamide at about 150-160° in an oil-bath. However, in the case of phenylacetaldehyde and furfuraldehyde, the condensation is easily effected in alcoholic solution. The alcoholic solution on warming under vigorous shaking deposits the anil.

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As these Schiff's bases are insoluble in the usual organic solvents, their purification offers considerable difficulty. Many of these compounds are simply ground in alcohol several times so as to dissolve any unreacted starting material filtered off, washed and dried. They are all coloured crystalline compounds, with sharp melting points and low solubility in water and are easily hydrolysed by weak acids. The results of their pharmacological examination are awaited.

EXPERIMENTAL

The anils from all the aldehydes except from those of furfuraldehyde and phenylacetaldehyde were prepared by the general procedure described for benzyli-dine-sulphanilamidothiazole.

Preparation of Benzyli-dine-sulphanilamidothiazole.—Sulphathiazole (1 g.) and pure redistilled benzaldehyde (0.5 g.) were mixed in a small round-bottom flask fitted with an air condenser and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 150°–160° for 3 hours. The mixture first melted and gradually became a pasty mass with small particles of water condensing on the cooler sides of the condenser. This was removed by applying gentle suction. After heating for 3 hours, the product was cooled and mixed with water. The solid was broken up and ground in a mortar to a fine powder and filtered and washed with water and alcohol, yield 1.2 g. (90% of theory), m.p. 202°.

The anils from furfuraldehyde and phenylacetaldehyde were prepared by mixing the molecular proportions of sulphathiazole (or sulphapyridine) and the aldehyde in alcoholic solution and slightly warming on a water-bath. The anils separated in fine yellow crystals.

The compounds prepared are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

R.	Aldehyde used.	Anils of sulphathiazole			Anils of sulphapyridine		
		M.p.	Nitrogen %		M.p.	Nitrogen %	
			Found.	Theo :		Found.	Theo
C_6H_5	Benzaldehyde	202°	12.02	12.25	240°	12.27	12.47
$p\text{-OMe}\cdot C_6H_4\text{-}$	Anisaldehyde	160°	11.37	11.23	205°	11.79	11.44
(3) OH, (4) OMe. $C_6H_3\text{-}$	Vanillin	245°	10.57	10.80	146-47°	10.84	10.96
3 : 4-(OMe) $_2$ $C_6H_3\text{-}$	Veratraldehyde	138°	10.15	10.42	210°	10.86	10.55
C_6H_5 . CH=CH	Cinnamaldehyde	260°	11.25	11.38	210°	10.91	11.42
$C_4H_5O\text{-}$	Furfuraldehyde	chars at 210°	12.40	12.61	214°	12.37	12.84
$m\text{-NO}_2$. $C_6H_4\text{-}$	<i>m</i> -Nitro-benzaldehyde	231°	14.20	14.43	254°	15.12	14.65
$m\text{-Cl}$. C_6H_4	<i>m</i> -Chloro-benzaldehyde	124°	10.84	11.13	101°	11.48	11.24
C_6H_5 . CH $_2\text{-}$	Phenyl-acetaldehyde	164°	11.77	11.76	100° (decomp.)	11.84	11.96